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THE DESIGN PHILOSOPHY OF THE ROOF: THE CENTURY OLD TAOIST TEMPLE IN KLANG VALLEY, MALAYSIA

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Abstract

The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) acknowledged the usefulness of any assets that demonstrate the historical context for regional sustainable growth, promoting peace, reconciliation, and the enhancement of cultural and biological diversity. The Taoist temple is conformable and recognisable. Its architectural design dates back to ancient China, the Zhou dynasty (1046–256 BCE). The artefact exhibits clearly and demonstrates Chinese cultural elements and historical relevance across civilizations. Nonetheless, urbanisation has progressed at the national level and exacerbated. The emergence of intriguing architectural buildings has had a significant impact on urban environments and their habitats. The physical and spatial buildings have been transformed significantly to fulfill the socioeconomic aspects. This global-scale issue has compounded the decrease in sustainable cultural value and Outstanding Universal Value. The goal of this study aims to distinguish the unique traits, characteristics and reveal the interpretation of design philosophy, specifically the roof of the Taoist temples built by the Chinese diaspora during the 19th century upon their arrival in Klang Valley, Malaysia. Targeted sampling was used and thereafter subjected to qualitative assessment for the roof design of the ten selected temples in terms of its physical, topological, and characteristics. The approach of content analysis was utilised to methodically evaluate the acquired material for the purpose of visual comparison and classification. The findings demonstrate that the primary method of constructing buildings is characterised by the use of Malay vernacular elements, whereas the implementation of the theory for quadrangles, essentially from Southern China, is comparatively less prevalent. Furthermore, a collective design philosophy was discovered, intentionally adopted by the theory of theism (神论), which was the representational of Figural, transforming the folklore stories. To achieve the goals stipulated by UNESCO, the author accentuates that the origin design philosophy for these century-old Taoist temples should be legally documented for advocating and preserving their Outstanding Universal Value. The involvement of lawful authorities, designers and stakeholders could potentially yield a fruitful outcome in strategic planning to preserve and maintain the cultural values of the temple, regardless of a renewal or new project.

Keywords: Architecture, Chinese Diaspora, Design Component, History & Cultural, Religious Building.